

Code Review Checklist

Please use the following checklist for reviewing the presented change. For each question check:

- “Yes” field – in case you have checked the code and everything is OK
- “No” field – in case you have checked the code and found some defects

If the item of the checklist does not apply or you did not check the code for it, please leave both columns unchecked.

General

<i>Yes</i>	<i>No</i>	
<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	Are all the changes relevant?
<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	Do the classes and methods fulfill their purpose?
<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	Are the messages and texts for the user correct?

Classes

<i>Yes</i>	<i>No</i>	
<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	Are all assignments of attributes correct?
<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	Are the classes implemented correctly? E.g., do they correctly implement inheritance and are they protected against unintentional access to their data?

Methods

<i>Yes</i>	<i>No</i>	
<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	Do methods always return a valid value?
<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	Do methods check parameters for validity (if needed)?
<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	Are all parameters used?

Arguments

<i>Yes</i>	<i>No</i>	
<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	Are the correct arguments used in all method calls?

Variables

<i>Yes</i>	<i>No</i>	
<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	Are all variables, counters and accumulators initialized properly and, if necessary, re-initialized each time they are used?
<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	Are all declared variables being used?

If-Then statements

<i>Yes</i>	<i>No</i>	
<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	Do the if-else statements fit the intended purpose?
<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	Are all edge cases handled?

Loops

<i>Yes</i>	<i>No</i>	
<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	Do the loops end under all possible conditions?
<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	Are the break and continue statements used properly?

Recursion

Yes | *No*
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Does the recursion terminate properly?

Errors

Yes | *No*
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Are the exceptions handled correctly?

Final Check

Yes | *No*
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Are all the changes consistent with each other?